

Biomechanical effects of rocker shoes in patients with plantar fasciitis

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Abstract

Plantar fasciitis is one of the most frequently occurring overuse injury of the foot and characterized by pain under the foot which aggravates during standing, walking and running. A frequently used treatment option for plantar fasciitis is the rocker shoe. The rocker shoe has a proximal apex position and a stiff insole. The rocker shoe is assumed to unload the plantar fascia during gait because it minimizes peak achilles tendon forces and dorsiflexion angles of the toes. However whether a proximal apex position and a stiff insole minimize the strain on the plantar fascia and how these two parameter interact has not been investigated yet.

A musculoskeletal model similar to a previously published study and data from a cadaver study was used to estimate the strain of the plantar fascia in ten healthy young adults and nine patients diagnosed with plantar fasciitis. The participants walked for 60 seconds on their comfortable speed on a treadmill. Four different shoe conditions were randomly applied by varying sole stiffness and the apex position of the shoe.

Plantar fascia strain remained unaffected by shoe condition, but peak Achilles tendon force, peak MTP1 angle and peak plantarflexion moment were significantly lower when walking with a proximal apex position and a stiff insole.

Rocker shoes with a stiff insole positively affect peak dorsiflexion angles of the toes and plantar flexion moments but not PA strain during gait. Possibly more proximal apex positions should be used in patients with plantar fasciitis to minimize plantar fascia strain during gait and facilitate healing processes.

Keywords Plantar fasciitis, gait, rocker shoes, apex position, musculoskeletal modelling

Introduction

Plantar fasciitis is a frequently occurring overuse injury of the foot (Buchbinder, 2004). Rocker shoes with a stiff insole are a commonly prescribed treatment modality used to alleviate complaints associated with plantar fasciitis (Crawford et al, 2003). The plantar fascia or plantar aponeurosis is a strong fibrous band which originates from the calcaneus and extends distal as five separate bundles to the phalanges (Stecco et al, 2013). The plantar fascia is connected to the paratenon of the Achilles tendon through the periosteum of the heel (Stecco et al, 2013). Due to its anatomy, mechanical stress of the PA increases with dorsiflexion of the metatarsophalangeal (MTP) joints and through the pulling force of the Achilles tendon (Stecco et al, 2013; Carlson et al, 2000). During gait, Achilles tendon forces are high, reflected by peak internal plantarflexion moments of approximately 1.5 Nm/kg bodyweight during push off (Perry et al, 1995). Furthermore dorsiflexion of the MTP joints increases after weight acceptance with peak values of approximately 35 degrees at the end of the stance phase (Leardini et al, 1999). Hence, during gait high mechanical loading of the plantar fascia occurs with every step. Considering the

pathophysiology of plantar fasciitis and the high mechanical loads of the PA during gait, a frequently used treatment modality is a rocker shoe with a stiff insole. Rocker shoes have a proximal apex which limits progression of the ground reaction forces and peak plantarflexion moments during gait. A stiff insole minimizes dorsiflexion of the toes. The aim of this study was to investigate whether the biomechanical effects of rocker shoes lead to minimization of plantar fascia strain during gait in patients with plantar fasciitis and healthy young adults.

Methods

8 patients with plantar fasciitis (1 male, 7 females; mean age 55.0 ± 8.4 years) and 8 healthy young adults (8 females; mean age 24.1 ± 1.6 years) participated in the study. Each participant walked for 1 minute on a treadmill while wearing normal shoes (65% apex) with flexible insoles (FN), normal shoes (65% apex) with stiff insoles (SN), rocker shoes (55 - 58% apex) with flexible insoles (FR) and rocker shoes with stiff insoles (SR). Marker position data of the foot and lower leg and ground reaction forces were recorded. An OpenSim foot model was used to compute the change in plantar fascia length based on changes in foot segment positions during gait. The effect of Achilles tendon force on plantar fascia strain was computed based on previous data of a cadaver study and added to the calculations (Carlson et al, 2000).

Results

Plantar fascia strain remained unaffected by shoe condition, but peak Achilles tendon force, peak MTP joint angles and peak plantarflexion moments were significantly lower when walking with rocker shoes and a stiff insoles ($p < .05$). Changes in Achilles tendon forces during gait accounted for $65 \pm 2\%$ of the total PA strain.

Conclusion and discussion

Rocker shoes with a stiff insole significantly reduce peak dorsiflexion angles and plantar flexion moments but not plantar fascia strain during gait. Possibly, because the rocker shoe affects peak Achilles tendon forces and MTP dorsiflexion angles at two different moments of the gait cycle, the effect of a proximal apex position and stiff insole does not add up leaving PA strain largely unaffected. Changes in Achilles tendon forces seem to be the main contributor on plantar fascia strain during gait. In severe cases of plantar fasciitis more proximal apex positions (<53%) might be used to alleviate complaints. In addition, clinicians might consider gait training to walk with smaller steps and at lower speeds leading to lower peak plantarflexion moments and therefore plantar fascia strain during gait.

References

- Buchbinder R (2004) Clinical practice. Plantar fasciitis. *N Engl J Med* 20;350(21):2159-66.
- Crawford F, Thomson C (2003) Interventions for treating plantar heel pain. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev* (3):CD000416.
- Stecco C, Corradin M, Macchi V, Morra A, Porzionato A, Biz C, De Caro R (2013) Plantar fascia anatomy and its relationship with Achilles tendon and paratenon. *J Anat* 223(6):665-76.

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Carlson RE, Fleming LL, Hutton WC (2000) The biomechanical relationship between the tendoachilles, plantar fascia and metatarsophalangeal joint dorsiflexion angle. *Foot Ankle Int* Jan;21(1):18-25.

Perry J, Burnfield JM (1995) *Gait Analysis: Normal and Pathological Function*. Slack Incorporated, Thorofare USA.

Leardini A, Benedetti MG, Catani F, Simoncini L, Giannini S (1999) An anatomically based protocol for the description of foot segment kinematics during gait. *Clin Biomech* 14(8):528-36.